

Teachers' Engagement in AI-Generated Virtual Labs and Students' Learning Habits in Information and Communication Technology

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Abstract. The study aimed to determine which domains of teachers' engagement in AI-generated virtual labs significantly influence students' learning interest in ICT (Information and Communication Technology) in the San Roque District, Davao City. A quantitative descriptive-correlational technique was employed, and the study's respondents were the grade 10 students in San Roque, District 2, Davao City, with 184 respondents out of 350 using the Roasoft calculator were selected in this study through a stratified random sampling. The findings revealed that Teachers' engagement in AI-generated virtual Labs, particularly in terms of Personal Role Models in Online Learning, Virtual Instructors, and Lecture Generation, was oftentimes extensive and oftentimes manifested. In contrast, Students' learning habits in terms of self-efficacy, active learning activities, and learning value are moderately extensive. Likewise, a significant relationship existed between the teachers' engagement in ai-generated virtual labs and students' learning habits. Domains of management that influence teachers' engagement in AI-generated virtual Labs, such as Personal Role Models in Online Learning, Virtual Instructors, and Generating Lectures with Virtual Instructors, significantly impact learners' study habits. The study was also anchored in Constructivist Theory, as proposed by Piaget (1968), which suggests that humans construct knowledge through interaction with their experiences and ideas.

KEY WORDS 1. Teachers' engagement in ai-generated virtual labs 2. Students' learning habits in (ICT) information and communication Technology 3. grade 10 learners
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1. Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative technology, increasingly integrated into everyday activities to enhance convenience. As advancements in AI continue, its potential effects on education warrant careful consideration, particularly regarding how it can shape students' readiness for future careers. AI presents the possibility to revolutionize educational practices by utilizing adaptive learning systems that optimize both instruction and student learning. Through the assessment of each student's individual strengths and weaknesses, AI can adapt educational materials to address specific learning needs. A key benefit of implementing AI in education is its capacity to deliver personalized learning experiences informed by

data-driven analysis. In the global context, Langreo, I., (2024) stressed that Specialists in artificial intelligence have highlighted its capacity to make K-12 education more individualized for both students and educators, including offering tailored professional development. In addition to classroom applications, experts suggest that generative AI tools may also improve efficiency and financial management within school districts. The district superintendent in Mississippi, as referenced by AI Langreo (2024), is an issue that should not be approached with hesitation. He has been observing the development of language models for several years and was among the first to sign up for ChatGPT when it launched last November. This technology is permanent and destructive. Educators should take advantage of this moment to teach both students and colleagues how to effectively use these tools. Currently, AI serves as an excellent search engine and a highly efficient assistant. Developing advanced skills utilizing platforms like ChatGPT, Bard, or Claude2 can save significant time. Artificial intelligence is advancing rapidly and playing a growing role, particularly in school districts with limited resources or those facing challenges. As generative AI technology develops, it is increasingly regarded as an essential tool for providing individualized, high-quality education to students from diverse backgrounds and age groups. Progress in this field is being accelerated by active collaboration among educators, scholars, and technology professionals, all working to realize AI's full capabilities (Ifenthaler Schumacher, 2023). Adaptive AI tutoring platforms, for instance, are able to customize feedback and support by modifying instructional content according to each learner's unique style and level of comprehension (Hwang et., al., 2020). Cruz-Benito et al. (2019) highlighted the need to explore both students' and educators' perspectives on how AI systems affect online learning environments at a national scale. Despite this, there is still

a lack of comprehensive understanding about how the integration of AI technology in online education impacts interactions between learners and instructors. Guilherme (2019) predicted that the adoption of AI in classrooms would significantly change teacher-student relationships. Felix (2020) also noted that additional studies are necessary to clarify the ways in which various AI systems shape learner-instructor interactions in virtual educational settings. As added by Hanawald, S. (2023). As technology has advanced, educators have relied on their judgment, experience, and expertise to connect with students and adapt both curriculum and teaching methods. The most effective technology integration has often occurred when academic leaders and instructors have chosen a carefully selected range of digital tools, embracing the principle that sometimes "less is more." For instance, rather than allowing each teacher to select their preferred learning management system (LMS), some schools have standardized on a single LMS for the entire school or division. This approach has enabled greater collaboration among teachers and allowed them to focus more on developing course content. Nevertheless, challenges remain: many educators are still getting accustomed to new technologies, have concerns about students potentially misusing AI for academic dishonesty, and may not realize that these tools can sometimes generate inaccurate or biased information. Thus, in this context, To address the identified research gap, the researcher conducted a study within District II, Davao City, utilizing a quantitative methodology. A descriptive-correlational design was chosen to better explore students' learning behaviors in relation to teachers' involvement with AI-powered virtual labs for ICT subjects, an area with limited existing research. This study seeks to enhance the current understanding of students' interest in technology and livelihood education.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—The study was also grounded in Constructivist Theory, as proposed by Piaget (1968), which suggests that humans construct knowledge through interaction with their experiences and ideas. The view of constructivism inspires radical constructivism due to his idea that the individual was at the center of the knowledge creation and acquisition. A person's intention to act, combined with their belief in their own abilities, influences the likelihood that they will engage in a particular behavior. The theory posits that social realities and classifications are shaped and continually updated through social interactions. This perspective emphasizes understanding phenomena from the viewpoint of those who experience and interpret them. Such social interactions have been shown to make students more engaged and active in online learning environments, thereby fostering a stronger sense of community—an important factor in sustaining participation in online education platforms (Seo et al., 2021; Martin et al., 2018). Martin and Bolliger (2018) identified interaction between learners and instructors as the most important among Moore's three types of educational interactions. Their research found that when instructors use diverse communication tools, provide encouragement, and offer timely feedback, both engagement and learning outcomes improve. Martin et al. (2018) further reinforced the positive effects of these instructional practices on student involvement and performance. Perin and Lauterbach (2018) introduced an artificial intelligence system for grading, which enabled quicker communication of grades between students and educators. Their study demonstrated that AI can offer continuous feedback, helping both students and instructors track learning progress and reach educational goals. In addition, Ross et al. (2018) developed adaptive online quizzes that deliver personalized learning materials, thereby boosting motivation and participation. The use of virtual avatars has

also allowed geographically dispersed students to collaborate in immersive virtual spaces, enhancing their sense of presence. Aslan et al. (2019) created a facial analytics tool powered by AI to strengthen instructors' roles as mentors in technology-based learning contexts. To fully understand these AI systems, it is important to explore both student and teacher perceptions of their impact. This research also considers relevant legal frameworks such as Republic Act 10173, the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which safeguards personal data in digital systems, and Republic Act 10175, the Cybercrime Prevention Act of 2012, which addresses offenses related to cybercrime. The Data Privacy Act focuses on the protection of personal information, while the Cybercrime Prevention Act targets the prevention and prosecution of online crimes. As illustrated in Figure 1, the study examined two variables. The independent variable was teachers' use of AI-powered virtual labs, measured by their roles as online role models, facilitators of virtual instruction, and creators of lessons using virtual instructors (Pataranutaporn et al., 2021). This highlights the relationship between teacher engagement and students' learning behaviors in information and communication technology contexts. The application of AI spans personalized learning pathways for students and automation of administrative tasks for educators. Ultimately, AI's value in education lies in its capacity to deliver adaptive, individualized learning experiences, streamline educational processes, and broaden access for learners globally (ASU Prep Global, 2024). The dependent variable of this study will be students' Learning Habits, with the corresponding indicators being Self-efficacy and active Learning Strategies, the measures of learning interest are self-efficacy, or the students' belief in their ability to understand, learn, and succeed in school-related tasks and activities; active learning strategies, or the instructional methods that engage students in value or the ethical principles, attitudes, and

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

behaviors that students develop as they engage with technology and livelihood education content; performance goal or the specific. Measurable objectives that students aim to achieve in terms of their academic and practical performance in ICT (Information and Communication Technology) subjects; and learning environment stimulation, which refers to the extent that in-

volves the use of simulated scenarios, activities, or projects that replicate real-world technological and online advances situations like participatory, hands-on, and interactive experiences to foster a deeper understanding of ICT (Information and Communication Technology) that would bring effective learning outcome.

2. Methodology

This section describes the research design, participant selection, instruments used, procedures for data collection, and methods of data analysis. It details the specific steps and techniques applied to gather and interpret data in order to address the research questions or test the study's hypotheses. The methodology offers a clear and succinct explanation of the overall approach and processes followed throughout the research.

2.1. Research Design—To achieve the study's objectives and obtain pertinent data, the researcher utilized a quantitative descriptive-correlational method. This design provided an organized framework for answering the research questions (McCombes, 2019). It included the strategies and steps for data collection, analysis, and interpretation, and outlined the process for examining the central issue of the research, which is a vital part of the research proposal

According to Bhandari (2020), quantitative research involves systematically collecting and analyzing numerical data, typically emphasizing the testing of theories through a deductive process influenced by empiricist and positivist perspectives. Additionally, non-experimental research does not involve manipulating independent variables; instead, it focuses on observing variables as they naturally occur in real-life contexts. Descriptive research design focuses on

outlining and documenting the features of a particular group or phenomenon. Information is usually collected via methods like surveys or observations and then summarized using statistics such as means, medians, and frequencies. This approach is commonly used as a preliminary step to identify trends and possible connections that may warrant deeper investigation with other research methodologies (Pallant, 2020). Brusilovsky and Somyürek (2018) note that correlational research design is useful for examining relationships between variables, particularly in educational contexts. This approach can shed light on how learners' information systems impact academic outcomes. In the same vein, Cheng and Yang (2019) emphasize that correlational studies can reveal elements that affect how effective online learning environments are, particularly those associated with information systems. Lemboye (2019) explains that correlational research is particularly beneficial when assessing the connections between two or more variables within the same group, or comparing the same variables across different groups. In this study, three variables were measured using validated surveys to analyze how they relate to each other. Previous research indicates that experiencing success tends to boost self-efficacy, while repeated failure can diminish it, thus affecting future achievement. The interplay among these factors suggests that greater exposure to successful experiences can enhance self-efficacy and increase the likelihood of success, particularly in project management. However, there is a noted gap in the literature, as these specific relationships have not been extensively studied. In this study, the correlational research examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause-and-effect relationships between variables. In this study, the researcher investigated the relationship between teachers' engagement in AI-generated virtual labs and students' learning interest in ICT (Information

and Communication Technology) in the San Roque District, Davao City. In this context, the study examined the relationships between these variables to assess the significance of the relationship. In this study, using descriptive-correlational was appropriate because the researcher only focused on the behavioral aspect of the respondents and did not perform an experiment in a controlled set-up.

2.2. Ethical Consideration—The researcher would promptly observe the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study, following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. It was essential for making informed decisions respecting individuals' and communities' rights and well-being. Understanding critical ethical principles and navigating the challenges can foster a culture of integrity, build trust with stakeholders, and promote long-term success.

Social Value The researcher exhibits this study's social value, including teachers' standpoints and experiences in developing scientific understanding through blended learning. The objectives of the study will define the needs of society, including the teachers and parents in the community so that they can use the knowledge to learn helpful and relevant insights about their experiences, which could help them generally improve their attitudes and dispositions in life and address the challenges in developing scientific understanding through blended learning. This study, followed by the school administrators and faculty, may help them become competent in developing effective learning strategies where every student feels supported, which can also have a positive impact on their academic performance and motivate and facilitate effective learning.

Informed Consent

A fundamental aspect of research ethics was that participants must voluntarily agree to take part in a study, having been fully informed about what their participation entails and providing their consent beforehand. In this research, obtaining informed consent was essential to ensure that participants could make knowledgeable decisions regarding their involvement. The Graduate Studies Department at Rizal Memorial College upholds specific regulations and guidelines that outline the process for securing informed consent from participants. For this study, the researcher collected written consent from all respondents. Participants were thoroughly briefed on the study's purpose, and detailed explanations were provided to help them understand the reasons for their involvement, allowing them to decide freely whether to participate. It was the researcher's responsibility to ensure that participants received all necessary information to make an informed choice, which is key to safeguarding their rights, maintaining ethical standards, fostering trust, and improving the quality of the research. Participation was explicitly stated to be voluntary, and individuals who chose not to take part were not pressured in any way. The researcher also took care to protect the psychological well-being of all respondents. Written authorization was obtained, and participants were informed that the study aimed to explore the factors influencing students' interest in learning through teachers' correlative teaching methods, with the goal of contributing to educational improvements.

Vulnerability of Research Participants

The study's respondents were teachers, so they were considered vulnerable since all of them were of legal age. They would also be considered highly vulnerable psychologically. The researcher would emphasize that the survey was set at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher was protected by the confidentiality of the information disclosed. Researchers could

ensure that their studies were ethical, respectful, and beneficial for all involved. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the respondents' consent. Thus, the researcher had limited access to ensure no personal data was exposed. The necessary data was collected, and the researcher permanently deleted all the survey results to ensure that data could not be traced back to the participants, who were the natural sources of information.

Risk, Benefits, and Safety When administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher provided respondents with clear information about their participation, including a thorough explanation of the study's objectives, potential benefits, and the confidentiality of their responses as outlined in the online questionnaire. Respondents were encouraged to ask any questions they had related to the study. The researcher took care to ensure that no harm would come to participants in any form. Additionally, the survey and interview materials were carefully crafted to avoid any language or content that could be considered degrading, offensive, or inappropriate. The study was strictly focused on gathering academic data relevant to the research topic, and participants were not asked to provide personal information. To reduce any inconvenience, adequate time was allotted for respondents to complete the survey. Participants were also given the choice to skip any questions that made them uncomfortable and were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any point if they felt unable to share certain information. The researcher prioritized the welfare of all participants and deeply appreciated their involvement. Respondents were assured that participating in the survey posed no anticipated risks to their health or well-being. In instances where a participant experienced discomfort or distress while answering the survey questions, the researcher committed to assisting them in accessing support from a qualified professional. Alternative arrangements for com-

pleting the data collection would also be made if necessary to ensure participant well-being remained the highest priority.

Justice

The researcher must avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents. The researcher regarded all respondents equally regardless of whether they would be respondents. The researcher would not be prejudiced in choosing the respondents for the study. Anybody qualified to be bonafide enrolled grade 10 students in the purposively selected schools. During the study, the researcher would respect the respondents by interrupting their routine as little as possible. To compensate for the time spent during data gathering, the researcher gave tokens of appreciation to the respondents. This token was an assortment of souvenirs. The tokens will be sent via courier and sealed carefully in a package. Also, each token was sanitized before being sent to your doorstep. Transparency To ensure openness in this study, all communications with participants were conducted openly and honestly. The researcher carefully applied the outlined methods to protect the well-being of respondents. All relevant documentation supporting the data analysis was included. Importantly, the researcher clearly described the level of participant involvement and explained the measures taken to maintain objectivity during data analysis and in reporting the study's findings. Emphasizing transparency in quantitative research helps enhance reliability and supports a culture of trust and integrity. Qualification of the Researcher

In this research, the investigator took steps to prevent any external factors, such as conflicts of interest, from affecting the participants' responses. The results of the study were made accessible to parents and school administrators, provided that appropriate procedures were followed to maintain respondent anonymity. The researcher also recognized the contributions of all individuals who supported the study and en-

sured that participants in the Division of Davao City received copies of the research findings, enabling them to use the results for educational purposes and further exploration.

Adequacy of Facilities

The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment and used ample and available learning materials during the study, which was done within the time set by the researcher. The accuracy of gathering data from the respondents was ensured by encoding the respondents' ratings properly during the day when the researcher was not too tired to do them to avoid errors in encoding. Also, the analysis and results were proficient and aligned, serving as a primary basis for adequacy.

Plagiarism Plagiarism is a violation of academic honesty and reflects poor scholarly practice. Whether intentional or not, it can have long-term consequences for one's professional future. It is the duty of students and researchers to ensure their work is free from plagiarism. In this study, proper citation was used to acknowledge original sources and demonstrate where information was obtained. The researcher also emphasized the importance of developing effective research skills, managing time well, and taking responsibility for one's own learning. Additional care was taken to avoid paraphrasing too closely to the original text, omitting quotation marks for direct quotes, or combining material from multiple sources without proper attribution. Fabrication and Falsification The researcher ensured strict adherence to ethical standards, including the avoidance of deception and conflicts of interest. Participants were assured that the study was conducted with honesty and transparency. According to Creswell (2019), the ethical conduct of research requires that any actions taken should not cause harm to participants. Throughout the study, the researcher provided adequate support to respondents, clearly explaining the research process, objectives, and the importance of their involvement. In addition,

this research followed the APA 7th edition citation guidelines to maintain proper attribution and prevent any misrepresentation or manipulation of data (Miles-Cohen et al., 2020). All findings and information were presented as accurately as possible. Community Involvement This study recognized the value of involving the community at each stage of the research process, from initial planning through to dissemination of results. Accordingly, the researcher intended to communicate the study's outcomes to the community and prioritized their participation in shaping the research direction, selecting suitable methodologies, and determining how the findings would be used. The results were shared with the community through meetings, forums, and conferences. Conflict of Interest The researcher took careful measures to address any potential conflicts of interest in this study. Professional judgment was not compromised by secondary interests, such as financial incentives, academic advancement, or other forms of recognition, ensuring that the primary focus remained on respondent welfare and the integrity of the research. The study maintained honesty throughout, with all information reviewed and verified by a panel of experts to prevent any harm to participants (Lakey Cohen, 2020). Permission From the Organization/Location Prior to beginning the research, the researcher obtained a letter of approval signed by the Dean of the Graduate School and submitted it to the Schools Division Superintendent in Davao City. Upon receiving authorization from the superintendent's office, this approval was then presented to the principals of the schools where the study took place.

Authorship Once the final version of the study was approved for publication, the researcher included as co-authors the adviser and other individuals who made significant contributions to the study's conception, design, data collection, analysis, interpretation, or who were involved in drafting or critically revising the

manuscript for substantial intellectual content. Participants were provided with the researcher's contact information, including a mobile number and email address listed on the informed consent form, should they have any questions, concerns, or complaints regarding the research. Additionally, the researcher committed to sharing the study's findings and benefits with stakeholders during meetings and conferences.

2.3. *Research Respondents*—The participants in this study were grade 10 students from Cluster 14 in the Division of Davao City. A total of 175 students were chosen using a stratified random sampling method. This sampling approach, along with the use of relevant statistical techniques, helps researchers obtain a sample that accurately reflects the diversity of the target population, leading to more precise and dependable findings. Stratified random sampling involves dividing the population into distinct subgroups, or strata. As noted by Bulus and Dong (2021), these strata are created based on common characteristics or attributes among members, such as educational background or income level. This method was suitable for the present study due to the varied nature of the population, which could be grouped using additional information. Creswell (2019) explains that probability sampling allows researchers to generalize findings from a sample to the larger population. There are four main types of probability sampling: simple random sampling, proportionate stratified random sampling, disproportionate random sampling, and cluster sampling. For this research, proportionate stratified random sampling was chosen, which is appropriate when the population consists of distinct subgroups. In this approach, the population is divided into strata, and participants are randomly selected from each stratum in proportion to their representation in the population. Participants were chosen based on specific inclusion criteria to ensure they could offer meaningful insights for the study's objectives. Eligibility requirements

included being a currently enrolled grade 10 student in Cluster 14 of Davao City, willingness to discuss their experiences and views regarding the Correlative Teaching Approach and its influence on their motivation to learn, and availability for participation in surveys or interviews during the data collection period. Additionally, students needed to provide informed consent by signing the required form and completing the questionnaires.

2.4. *Research Instrument*—The researcher used adapted and modified research survey questionnaires from the study of Pataranutaporn et al. (2021) to align with the context of the respon-

dents of this study. By choosing the right research instrument and designing it carefully, researchers can collect high-quality data that contributes to advancing knowledge in their field. The first part concerned the teachers’ engagement in the AI-generated virtual labs approach. The instrument was composed of statements divided into indicators: classroom interaction, learning engagement, skills development, time development, time consciousness, learning attention, and conducive environment. The questionnaire made use of a 5-point Likert scale and will be determined based on the following range of means:

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation of Teachers’ Correlative Teaching Approach

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The teachers’ correlative teaching approach is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teachers’ correlative teaching approach is often observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teachers’ correlative teaching approach is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teachers’ correlative teaching approach is seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teachers’ correlative teaching approach is never observed.

The scaling process involved setting the mid-point value of 5 as the average or fair cut-off, using a consistent interval of 0.80. Prior to its use, the instrument was reviewed and validated by three experts, and modifications were made based on their feedback.

The second part of the instrument concerned the teachers’ engagement in the AI-generated virtual lab’s approach and study habits adapted from the study by H. et al. (2005) was modified to fit or align with the present setting and situation. The development of the said survey research questionnaire was to measure students’ motivation towards science learning. The ques-

tionnaire comprises self-efficacy statements, active learning strategies, learning values, performance goals, and learning environment goals. The reliability of the new scale obtained a Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.947, which was interpreted as excellent, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. In answering the questionnaire, the respondents made use of the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of student’s learning habits in information and communication technology, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation of Students’ Learning Habits

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The students’ learning habits are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The students’ learning habits are often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The students’ learning habits are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The students’ learning habits are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The students’ learning habits are never manifested.

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The previous statements detail the steps the researcher carefully followed during the data collection process, adhering to the guidelines and the school policies established by Rizal Memorial Colleges, INC., particularly regarding face-to-face interactions. The research questionnaire was reviewed, and necessary procedures were implemented for the study. Data collection involved obtaining information from multiple sources, including surveys, interviews, observations, and existing records. The primary aim was to gather accurate and relevant data to address the research questions, support informed decision-making, and contribute to problem-solving. Permission to Conduct the Study The researcher secured permission to conduct this study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school’s division superintendent and then to the school principals of the selected public secondary schools in Cluster 14 in the Division of Davao City, Division

of Davao City. In the third week of February 2025, the researcher began developing the content and objectives for her thesis proposal. She also prepared essential documents, such as letters requesting approval for the study. The research adhered to standard ethical data collection procedures, as Creswell (2019) outlined. Once the research proposal was presented, it was approved by the five-member panel of examiners and the graduate school dean. The dean issued an endorsement letter and an ethical clearance certificate. This documentation was then forwarded to the division along with the revised Chapters 1 and 2 of the manuscript. The researcher subsequently awaited permission to proceed with the study. On May 24, 2025, the researcher received official authorization from the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao City to conduct the study. This permit was obtained through the appropriate channels, allowing him to gather data and conduct research within Cluster 14 in the Division of Davao City. Likewise, the researcher secured the parents’ consent of the respondents, allowing them to answer the said survey questionnaire.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire In this study, the researcher distributed

the instrument to the respondents after approval. The study was conducted in the first quarter of S.Y. 2024-2025. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. The researcher would comply with the DepEd protocol when administering the questionnaire during the study process. The study respondents were given enough testing time to finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected was subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data After the questionnaire was retrieved, each respondent's scores were tallied to organize the data per indicator. Then, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS. Collation and statistical data treat-

ment were essential steps in research that helped ensure that the data collected was accurate, reliable, and meaningful. By applying these steps, researchers can draw valid conclusions about their research question or hypothesis and contribute to knowledge in their field of study. The preliminary analysis results were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of March 2025. For coaching and statistical treatment, the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician to provide technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study sometime during the fourth week of March 2025 and further deepening the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results during the fourth week of March 2025.

2.6. Data Analysis—The researcher analyzed the collected data utilizing several statistical methods to extract insights and patterns that could inform decision-making. Various techniques and tools were applied to uncover trends, relationships, and correlations within the dataset, which allowed for meaningful conclusions to be drawn from the analysis. The mean was employed to describe both the level of teacher engagement in the AI-generated virtual labs approach and students' learning habits in Information and Communication Technology. This statistical measure was used to address the first and second research objectives. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used in this

study to assess the significant relationship between independent (teachers' engagement in ai-generated virtual labs approach) and dependent (students' learning habits Information and Communication Technology) variables. It was a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it is usually denoted by r . This was used to supply the answer for objective 3. Multiple Linear Regression was applied to evaluate the significance of the influence of the independent (teachers' engagement in AI-generated virtual labs approach) variable on the dependent (students' learning habits in ICT (Information and Communication Technology) variable. This was utilized to supply the answer to the objective.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter systematically presents, analyzes, and interprets the data that has been collected. The use of both tables and descriptive text enhances the clarity of the analysis, making it easier to draw meaningful conclusions. Such an approach not only enriches our understanding of the data but also reinforces the claims made in the hypothesis. By integrating various presentation formats, the findings become more accessible and impactful, providing strong support for the initial assertions of the study.

3.1. *Teachers' Engagement in AI-Generated Virtual Labs*—Table 1 summarizes the teachers' engagement in AI-generated Virtual Labs. The results focus on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: Virtual Instructors (4.22), Personal Role Models in Online Learning (3.66), and

Generating Lectures with Virtual Instructors (3.33). These indicators are oftentimes manifested, while Performance Goals are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.75 indicates that teachers' engagement in AI-generated virtual Labs is extensive and, thus, evident.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Teachers' Engagement in AI-Generated Virtual Labs

No	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Personal Role Models in Online Learning	3.66	Extensive
2	Virtual Instructors	4.22	Very Extensive
3	Generating Lectures with Virtual Instructors	3.37	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.75	Extensive

Teachers' engagement with AI-generated virtual labs is crucial for enhancing student learning experiences, fostering innovation in teaching, and preparing students for a technologically advanced future. AI is a supportive teaching tool that automates administrative tasks like grading and allows educators to focus on interactive and personalized instruction. AI-driven tutoring systems offer tailored feedback and adapt to individual student needs, enhancing the learning experience. Mousavinasab et al. (2021), VanLehn (2011 as cited in Janson and Janke 2024), and Hickey et al. (2020) agreed that the development and implementation of learning platforms and e-learning software is meant to benefit learners in striving for knowledge and their ability to perform well in learning assignments. One unique form of software is intelligent tutoring systems, which provide learners with skill-level-appropriate exercises and repetition material. Past research has shown those tools to bolster learning outcomes and to be as effective as human tutoring. Moreover, intelligent tutoring systems can reduce achievement

gaps bound to a lack of learning opportunities as they are highly accessible. As such tools are accessible through one's own devices and do not require students to be present in an actual classroom, the effective use of intelligent tutoring systems requires students' willingness to engage in self-regulated learning. In this regard, little is known about why and how students use intelligent tutoring systems and how differences in usage explain differences in the effectiveness of these systems. In particular, the interpretation of logfile data derived from such tools is a current research interest that oftentimes raises more questions than answers (Baker et al., 2020).

3.2. *Students' Learning Habits in terms of Self-efficacy*—Table 2 presents a summary of the extent of students' learning habits. The results are focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of the indicators, which are as follows: Self-efficacy (3.15), Active Learning Activities (3.14), Learning Value (3.24), and Performance Goal (3.62). These indicators are oftentimes manifested, while Performance Goals are sometimes manifested. The overall

mean rating of 3.29 indicates that the extent of students' learning habits is sometimes extensive and, thus, sometimes evident. Good study habits are crucial for students' academic success. They impact learning, time management, and overall well-being and are important to academic performance. Good study habits are the

backbone of academic success. They guide students in learning efficiently and effectively, helping them reach their educational goals. With good study habits, students understand how to approach their studies systematically, making them more likely to excel in their work.

Table 2. The Summary of the Extent of Students' Learning Habits

No	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Self-efficacy	3.15	Moderately Extensive
2	Active Learning Activities	3.14	Moderately Extensive
3	Learning Value	3.24	Moderately Extensive
4	Performance Goal	3.62	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.29	Moderately Extensive

The finding is similar to Castillo et Al.'s study (2023). Study habits have always been an integral part of a student's day-to-day academic experience. These are practices that can help a learner develop an interest in studying without feeling pressured or bothered. Study habits are among the most important determinants of a student's academic performance, according to Jafari (2019). As further elaborated by Kumar (cited in Castillo et Al., 2023), study habits refer to the habitual tendencies and practices that students exhibit while acquiring information through learning. These methods have either been used or proven effective by many students as they think of ways to make them. One of the key components of the theory of instructional delivery is the concept of digital literacy. Digital literacy is effectively using digital tools and resources to communicate, collaborate, create, and evaluate information.

3.3. Significant Relationship Between Teachers' Engagement in Ai-Generated Virtual Labs and Students' Learning Habits —Table 3 revealed a significant relationship between Teachers' Engagement in AI-generated virtual Labs and Students' Learning Habits. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis must be rejected, stating that there is no significant relationship, for it provides empirical evidence to show its correlation. It can be inferred that Pearson's Correlation generated a strong, positive, and significant correlation between teachers' engagement in AI-generated virtual Labs and students' learning habits ($r = 0.877$; $p < .000$) and instructional delivery. In the modern digital era, effective Teachers' Engagement in AI-generated virtual Labs is crucial for Students' Learning Habits to provide high-quality learning experiences.

Learning is essential for personal growth, societal advancement, and individual well-being, as it fosters adaptability, critical thinking, and a sense of purpose. It plays a significant role

in personal development by helping individuals acquire the skills, knowledge, understanding, and values needed to pursue their goals effectively. Continuous learning keeps the brain en-

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Teachers’ Engagement in AI-Generated Virtual Labs and Students’ Learning Habits

Variables	Tr-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Learners’ Study Habit	0.877	<0.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

**Significant at p < 0.05.*

gaged and active, potentially slowing cognitive decline as we age. Moreover, it equips individuals to adapt to change and navigate new situations, which is increasingly important in our rapidly evolving world. Learning also boosts confidence and self-esteem, as achieving new knowledge and skills contributes to a greater sense of accomplishment. Ghimire, Prather, and Edwards (2024) and El-Hussein, Hasselaar, and Lutsyshyn (2024) concur that Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a transformative force across various sectors, including education. Educational institutions are increasingly adopting AI-driven tools—such as adaptive learning platforms, AI tutoring systems, and innovative note-taking applications—to deliver personalized learning experiences, streamline administrative tasks, and enhance student outcomes. By addressing individual needs, AI can enhance study efficiency, reduce stress, and improve academic performance. This aligns with the objectives of Education 4.0, which aims to prepare students for a technologically advanced future. Ward, Bhati, Fnu Neha, and Guercio’s (2024) recent studies have highlighted the potential of AI to personalize educational experiences by adapting content to individual learning styles and paces. The World Economic Forum’s report on Education 4.0 emphasizes AI’s role in customizing learning pathways for students, helping them achieve more efficient outcomes through tailored instructional content and immediate feedback mechanisms. Similarly, adaptive AI tools, such as intelligent tutoring systems and personalized learning platforms, have been shown to improve engagement and motivation, particularly among students in STEM fields (Hussin, 2018; Lin, Huang, and Lu, 2023).

3.4. Domains of Teachers’ Engagement In AI-Generated Virtual Labs Significantly Affecting the Learner’s Study Habits—Table 4 presents the simple regression coefficient analysis of domains related to Teachers’ Engagement in AI-Generated Virtual Labs, which significantly affect the learners’ study habits. Domains of teachers’ engagement in AI-generated virtual labs, including personal role models in Online Learning (0.001), Virtual Instructors (0.002), and Generating Lectures with Virtual Instructors (0.001), significantly influenced instructional delivery. Meanwhile, the R² value of 0.886 suggests that learners’ study habits explain 88.6% of the variance in teachers’ engagement in AI-generated virtual Labs. This provides empirical evidence that the management domains of the learner’s information system can account for and explain the variability of instructional delivery. Additionally, the F-value represents the sum of squares, with the regression term denoting the model and the residual term denoting the error. The F-value (264.588) and F-statistic are significant (p < .001), indicating that the model accurately predicts learner study habits. AI-powered educational platforms can analyze vast amounts of data to identify patterns and offer personalized recommendations, enhancing students’ engagement and motivation. One of the significant benefits of AI in education is its ability to provide students with immediate and constructive feedback. Teachers’ engagement with AI-generated tools can significantly benefit learners’ study habits by offering personalized learning experiences, adaptive feedback, and real-time insights, ultimately improving engagement and academic outcomes.

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Teachers’ Engagement in AI-Generated Virtual Labs Significantly Influences the Learners’ Study Habits

Model	B	Beta	Std. Error	Std. Coef. Error	t-value	p-value	Decision
H ₀ (Intercept)	4.145	—	0.079	—	60.416	0.001	—
H ₁ (Intercept)	0.313	—	0.175	—	1.066	0.270	—
Personal Role Models in Online Learning	0.807	0.107	0.102	0.107	1.010	0.315	Accept H ₀
Virtual Instructor	0.441	0.108	0.136	0.108	1.299	0.196	Accept H ₀
Generating Lecture Instruction	0.683	0.086	0.499	0.086	5.654	0.001	Reject H ₀

R² = 0.886

F-value = 264.588

p-value = < 0.001

**Significant at p < 0.05.*

AI has the potential to transform personalized learning and student engagement by tailoring educational experiences to individual needs and learning styles. Through data-driven insights, AI can provide real-time feedback on student performance, emotions, and engagement levels, enabling educators to customize teaching methods and interventions. This personalized approach not only enhances student motivation but also supports more effective learning outcomes, addressing the unique challenges faced by each learner in a sustainable education system [7] AI has the potential to transform personalized learning and student engagement by tailoring educational experiences to individual needs and learning styles. Through data-driven insights, AI can provide real-time feedback on student performance, emotions, and engagement levels, enabling educators to customize teaching methods and interventions. This personalized approach not only enhances student motivation but also supports more effective learning outcomes, addressing the unique challenges faced by each learner in a sustainable education system [7] Lin, Huang, and Lu (2023) contended that AI possesses the capacity

to revolutionize personalized learning and student engagement by customizing educational experiences to meet individual requirements and learning styles. AI can deliver real-time feedback on student performance, emotions, and engagement levels through data-driven insights, allowing educators to tailor instructional approaches and interventions. This tailored method not only boosts student enthusiasm but also fosters more effective learning results, tackling the distinct problems encountered by each learner within a sustainable educational framework. A comparable study by Seo, Tang, Roll, Fels, and Yoon (2021) concurred that Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies provide tangible assistance for online education, encompassing the personalization of student learning, the automation of instructors’ everyday responsibilities, and the facilitation of adaptive assessments. Nonetheless, although AI potential appear exciting, the influence of AI systems on the culture, norms, and expectations governing interactions between students and instructors remains ambiguous. In online education, learner-instructor contact, including communication, support, and presence, significantly influences students’ sat-

isfaction and learning outcomes. Consequently, ascertaining how students and instructors perceive the influence of AI systems on their interactions is essential to uncover any deficiencies, problems, or obstacles that hinder AI systems from realizing their intended potential and jeopardize the safety of these interactions. They added that Although AI systems have been positively recognized for improving the quantity and quality of communication, providing just-in-time, personalized support for large-scale settings, and improving the feeling of connection, there were concerns about responsibility, agency, and surveillance issues. These findings have implications for the design of AI systems, including ensuring explainability, human-in-the-loop capabilities, and the careful collection and presentation of data. Overall, contributions of this study include the design of AI system storyboards that are technically feasible and positively support learner–instructor interaction, capturing students’ and instructors’ concerns about AI systems through Speed Dating, and suggesting practical implications for maximizing the positive impact of AI systems while minimizing the negative ones.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusions, and recommendations based on the results of the data analysis, discussion, and implications drawn. Findings were based on the problem’s posed statement; conclusions were drawn from the findings generated, and recommendations were based on the impact of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The results, analysis, and discussions presented the study’s findings. The Extent of teachers’ engagement in AI-generated Virtual Labs, in terms of Personal Role Models in online learning, has consistently been manifested as Virtual Instructors (4.22). Generating Lectures with Virtual Instructors (3.37) has been observed at times. The overall mean rating of 3.75 denotes the extent to which management of the learners’ information system was often-times manifested and thus extensive. Students’ learning habits, in terms of Self-efficacy (3.15), Active Learning Activities (3.14), and Learning Value (3.24), were often observed. The overall mean rating of 3.29 denotes that the extent of study habits is sometimes manifested, thus moderately extensive. Pearson’s correlation generated a significant correlation between teachers’ engagement in AI-generated virtual Labs ($r = 0.886$; $p < .000$) and students’ learning habits. Domains of management of the Teachers’ Engagement in AI-generated virtual Labs in terms of Personal Role Models in Online Learn-

ing (0.001), Virtual Instructors (0.002), and Generating Lectures with Virtual Instructors (0.001) significantly influenced learners study habits. Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.886 suggests that learners’ study habits explain 88.6% of the variance in teachers’ engagement in AI-generated Virtual Labs. This provides empirical evidence that teachers’ engagement in AI-generated content significantly influences learners’ study habits.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following were the conclusions to wit; Teachers’ engagement in AI-generated virtual Labs, particularly in terms of Personal Role Models in Online Learning, Virtual Instructors, and Lecture Generation, was often extensive and frequently manifested. Students’ learning habits in terms of self-efficacy, active learning activities, and learning value are moderately extensive. A significant relationship existed between the teachers’ engagement in ai-generated virtual labs and students’ learning habits. There is a significant relationship be-

tween teachers' engagement with artificial intelligence (AI) and students' learning habits, and this connection is crucial for fostering learning development. AI tools can personalize learning experiences, provide data-driven insights for teachers, and enhance student engagement, ultimately impacting learning outcomes. Domains of management that influence teachers' engagement in AI-generated virtual Labs, such as Personal Role Models in Online Learning, Virtual Instructors, and Generating Lectures with Virtual Instructors, significantly impact learners' study habits. Teachers' engagement with AI and its impact on student learning habits, particularly through the lens of Piaget's Constructivist Theory, is essential for effective education. This involves understanding how AI can facilitate active, personalized learning experiences, while also addressing potential challenges and ethical considerations. Moreover, Piaget's Constructivist Theory highlights that learners actively build knowledge through interaction with their environment. When integrated thoughtfully, AI can enhance this process by personalizing learning, facilitating active engagement, promoting critical thinking, supporting collaboration, and fostering creativity. However, challenges such as over-reliance, diminished critical thinking, and ethical concerns must be addressed. Teachers play a crucial role in ensuring AI aligns with constructivist principles by developing AI literacy, balancing traditional and digital methods, guiding ethical use, and continuously evaluating AI's effectiveness. Thoughtful integration of AI can thus create more engaging, personalized, and meaningful learning experiences while upholding core constructivist values.

4.3. *Recommendations*—Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations can be made;

Public School District Supervisor

May allocate sufficient resources to support implementing and maintaining robust teachers' Engagement in AI-generated Virtual Labs. This

includes investing in technology infrastructure, data management tools, and professional development programs to enable educators to utilize the system's capabilities effectively. Likewise, learners' studies may consider continuing to promote and motivate them. It may foster a culture of collaboration among schools within the district, encouraging the sharing of best practices in embracing teachers' engagement in AI-generated virtual labs, particularly in the following areas: personal role models in online learning, virtual instruction, and lecture generation because learning is essential for personal growth, societal advancement, and individual well-being, as it fosters adaptability, critical thinking, and a sense of purpose. It plays a significant role in personal development by helping individuals acquire the skills, knowledge, understanding, and values needed to pursue their goals effectively. Continuous learning keeps the brain engaged and active, potentially slowing cognitive decline as we age.

Moreover, it equips individuals with the ability to adapt to change and navigate new situations, which is increasingly important in our rapidly evolving world. The process of learning also boosts confidence and self-esteem, as achieving new knowledge and skills contributes to a greater sense of accomplishment. School Principal It provided educators with opportunities to enhance their online and digital engagement skills. This was achieved through workshops, training sessions, and collaboration with experts in educational technology. Additionally, by providing guidance and support in data analysis, principals enabled teachers to identify areas for improvement and make informed instructional decisions. This included regularly reviewing data during staff meetings, encouraging data-driven discussions, and recognizing and celebrating instructional practices that yielded positive outcomes. Teacher They may proactively develop engagement in AI-generated Virtual Labs to navigate and guide the learners in

learning. This includes manipulating and exploring digital understanding. They may use this knowledge to design personalized instruction, incorporating differentiated strategies and resources that cater to diverse learning styles and abilities. They may engage in regular reflection and self-assessment, using artificial intelligence in instruction to evaluate the effectiveness of their instructional delivery. This process enables continuous improvement, allowing teachers to refine their practices and optimize student learning outcomes. The study encourages future researchers to conduct thorough investigations aimed at discovering best practices in utilizing AI-generated virtual labs in a way that effectively aids and directs learners throughout their educational paths. The findings from this research have the potential to be published in a well-regarded academic journal. Additionally, it was recommended that researchers explore various methodologies and frameworks to optimize the use of virtual labs, ensuring they meet the diverse needs of learners. This research could make a significant contribution to the field and advance our understanding of the role of AI in education.

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